

WHITE PAPER

AI and Foundational Models

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**EUROPEAN TECHNOLOGY
PLATFORM FOR HIGH
PERFORMANCE COMPUTING**

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Executive Summary

This is a white paper released as part of the ETP4HPC's Strategic Research Agenda 6.

This white paper focuses on the theme of AI and Foundation Models, providing a comprehensive overview of the current landscape and future direction of AI technologies, as they relate to supercomputing. Its objective is to guide the future of AI research and development, ensuring that frontier models continue to evolve and benefit various sectors while addressing ethical, environmental, and technical challenges.

We explore the dynamic and rapidly evolving landscape of Artificial Intelligence (AI) with a focus on foundation models. These models, which form the backbone of numerous AI applications, are pivotal in driving advancements across various sectors; from healthcare and education to industry and quantum computing. Finally, we describe the key thematic areas of frontier models and our recommended approach to developing comprehensive and impactful datasets and benchmarks for these.

Glossary of acronyms

AI - Artificial Intelligence

AL - Active Learning

APU - Accelerated Processing Unit

BSI - British Standards Institute

FM - Foundation Model

GPU - Graphics Processing Unit

ISO - International Organization for Standardization

IPU - Integrated Processing Unit

LLM - Large Language Model

RAG - Retrieval Augmented Generation

RL - Reinforcement Learning

TPU - Tensor Processing Unit

Key Topics & Recommendations

This section highlights the following key topics and recommendations for policymakers and stakeholders, emphasising the importance of frontier models in various sectors and their implications for supercomputing research.

AI at scale

- AI has found several applications in accelerating heavy computation, surfacing knowledge, and aiding real-time control. Heavy AI workflows include but are not limited to foundation models (FMs), reinforcement learning (RL), active learning (AL), and uncertainty quantification (UQ).
- AI and its interplay with other workflows encompass a variety of models and architectures, but they all require dedicated supercomputing resources even though at different stages.
- Successful AI models have benefited both from new architectures and from advancements in hardware for parallel computing, high performance storage and few-bit algebra on older HPC system architectures.
- AI models can be very large themselves or be smaller components within heavy numerical simulations or experiment campaigns that must be trained and refined in closed loop.
- Inference - AI at scale is increasingly influenced by the growing computational demands of inference, which, like training, is becoming more resource intensive. As models become more complex and widely deployed in production environments, inference workloads are scaling up significantly, often requiring an ever-increasing number of compute nodes to achieve low-latency predictions. This trend is driving the need for larger, parallel workloads that can process vast amounts of data simultaneously, leveraging distributed computing resources. Efficient scaling of inference is now as critical as training, demanding robust infrastructure to handle the massive

parallelism required for real-time and batch processing.

- **Frontier Models** – bleeding edge, highly advanced machine learning models that push the boundaries of current technologies. These models are often larger, more complex, and more powerful than previous iterations, capable of handling diverse and sophisticated tasks. They are often designed for general-purpose applications, spanning across multiple domains such as natural language processing, computer vision, and decision-making. Examples are Anthropic's Claude, and DeepMind's Gato or Astra. These models represent the frontier of AI research, aiming to bridge the gap between specialized models and artificial general intelligence (AGI).

Foundation Models

- Foundation models are AI models that can be trained once and are dynamically re-adapted for a variety of downstream tasks.
- **Emerging Capabilities:** attention-based AI models learn to recognise relationships and context in language and images, and are evolving to handle more complex tasks, including (but not limited to) text and image generation.
- **Specialisation:** Techniques such as fine-tuning, prompt re-configuration, and retrieval augmented generation (RAG) are critical to tailor models to specific fields or domains.
- **Multi-modality:** Beyond text, foundation models are now integrating visual, speech, and video data, enabling more comprehensive and versatile applications. Notable areas include protein languages, genomics, and sensor data processing.

Architectural Innovations

- Developing **novel architectures** that can represent multiple modalities and learn them in a robust and efficient way.
- **Beyond transformers:** Exploration of alternative architectures like State Space Models and xLSTM that offer different strengths and efficiencies. Kolmogorov-Arnold Networks (KAN) are alternatives that are being introduced.
- **Scalability:** Addressing the challenges and opportunities presented by models with trillions of parameters (e.g. the *Trillion Parameter Consortium*) including issues related to training costs, inference efficiency, and environmental impact. Efficient algorithms must be developed to train large models, to reduce environmental impact and serve the trained models to the wider population. Advancements include new methods for numerical linear algebra, pruning, and quantized models.
- **Data representations:** different modalities embeddings and retrieval algorithms for RAG can help establish meaningful relationships among data and reduce hallucinations in Foundation Models' query responses.
- **Data closer to the models:** some hardware solutions (e.g. AMD, Graphcore, Groq) keep training data as close as possible to the model, suitably partitioned, to ensure efficient training and deployment.
- **Emerging hardware:** neuromorphic and quantum computing differ from the classical computing architectures, and potentially may bring a similar performance leap as GPUs did for large neural networks.

Ethics and Safety Implications

The application of AI to several fields has encountered aspects of ethics that are common to other technologies. Ensuring that AI models are ethical, explainable, and free from biases is paramount. Developing robust benchmarks for performance evaluation and adhering to AI

regulations are critical for maintaining trust and reliability in AI systems. Within the wider field of Responsible Innovation, AI Ethics inherit challenges and guidelines, as well as posing new challenges. Increasingly powerful AI models accelerate technological discoveries, thereby increasing the risk of dual or malicious use. Some powerful techniques such as AL and RL can be prone to catastrophic forgetting during wider exploration of novel examples and scenarios. Larger deep-learning based models tend to be more expressive but also less explainable than e.g. tree-based algorithms. Safety-critical aspects must also be considered: RL agents can be prone to unintended behaviours ("reward hacking"), LLMs can be prone to hallucinations, providing confident but unsafe recommendations, and to prompt-injection attacks that can reveal part of the training corpus. It should also be noted that the EU AI Act classifies very large models as posing systemic risks and requiring tighter scrutiny and regulatory oversight. We provide a summary of challenges, possible mitigation strategies, and published guidelines.

Applications and Use Cases

- **Healthcare:** AI-driven virtual assistants, based on FMs supporting clinical trial analysis and automated medical record dictation, are transforming patient care and administrative efficiency. AI-aided analyses can also help predict clinical pathways and aid in biomedical imaging, tomography and drug discovery.
- **Education:** Personalized learning experiences, automated student feedback, and content creation tailored to individual needs can enhance educational outcomes. Similarly, federated platforms will enrich e-learning material and serve the EU learning ecosystem and beyond.
- **Regulatory Compliance:** AI applications in document review, policy generation, and legal compliance can streamline processes and improve accuracy. This is specifically important in the interconnected legal system of the EU.

- **Scientific and Industrial Sectors:** Scalable AI models are making significant strides in scientific computing, smart cities, aerospace, and manufacturing, enhancing productivity and innovation, optimal allocation and planning. We should not exclude simulation workflows that will be more enhanced and focussed. Accelerated heavy calculations include structural engineering and fluid dynamics, hazardous material spillage, weather and climate, and design of complex facilities. Many of these challenges are tackled more efficiently at EU level. Workflows have been developed, with embedded AI acceleration, to problems that are inherently multi-scale [1,2,3].
- **Arts, Humanities and the Creative sector:** Generative AI can swiftly generate and draft content (pictures, text, scenarios, scripts), lowering the entry barrier to proof-of-concept creative processes. This has led to renewed attention on its implications e.g. on deepfakes and intellectual property. AI can also be used for information retrieval and semantic segmentation, also aiding the digitalisation and research on historical artefacts.

Quantum and AI

- **Circuit Compilation:** AI's role in optimising quantum circuits demonstrates the synergy between AI and quantum computing.
- **Problem Embedding:** AI models are effectively mapping complex problems to quantum hardware, paving the way for new quantum applications.
- **Quantum optimisers:** techniques from quantum computing can be used to devise more efficient training algorithms for classical architectures.

This should be read in conjunction with the white paper on [Quantum for HPC](#). We must stress that quantum computing is currently an emerging technology (in hardware, software and applications) while AI and HPC are high-TRL.

Trends and Future Outlook

We outline the latest trends in AI, including advancements in multi-modal AI, the integration of AI in edge devices, and the move towards more sustainable and explainable AI systems. It also presents a vision for the post-exascale era, highlighting the potential of AI to drive further technological breakthroughs.

Key Recommendations

- **Policy Support:** Encourage policies that support the development and deployment of advanced AI models, ensuring ethical standards and regulatory compliance.
- **Funding Initiatives:** Advocate for targeted funding to support research in domain-aware AI.
- **Collaborative Efforts:** Promote collaboration between academia, industry, and government to foster innovation and address the challenges associated with AI development.

Key Thematic Areas

Emerging Capabilities of AI Models

Generative models have demonstrated unprecedented capabilities in natural language processing and generation. These models are continuously being refined to handle more complex and diverse tasks, enhancing their utility across different domains.

Specialisation Techniques of LLMs

Fine-tuning and pre-training for specific fields enable the creation of models that are highly specialised and efficient for particular applications. Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) is another key technique that enhances the ability of models to generate contextually relevant responses by integrating external knowledge sources. Chain of Thought (CoT) and Tree of Thought (ToT) are techniques that try to elicit reasoning-like behaviour from these models, increasing the quality and the explainability of the answers. One major limitation for adapting LLMs to solve particular tasks is the availability of suitable benchmark/evaluation datasets. Multiple Choice Questions (MCQ) are often used because they are easy to implement and evaluate, but evaluating the quality of an answer that involves reasoning is still very challenging, and typically involves extensive and costly human involvement.

Multi-modality

Modern AI systems are increasingly integrating multiple data modalities, including text, speech, imaging, and video. This approach allows for more comprehensive and versatile applications, extending the reach of AI to areas such as protein languages and genomics.

Image segmentation has benefited from foundation models, both with “classical” convolutional architectures and with vision transformers. Few-shot segmentation frameworks rely on large datasets of annotated images (over one billion for the *Segment Anything* class [4]), and can be quickly fine-tuned to recognise more

niche object classes in specific applications, e.g. manufacturing or security. Consistent scene recognition, segmentation and tracking in video data is an active research field. In autonomous-vehicle applications, petabytes of data are collected in order to query for image similarity (e.g. with visual-question-answering approaches [5]) and recognise problematic scenes for safety studies. Efficiently streaming such data volumes for training on HPC is an outstanding bottleneck across traditional HPC.

Speech models [6] would be widely useful in an inherently multi-lingual EU. Outstanding challenges are limited data size, limited variety of audio quality and of accents; speaker, phoneme, and emotion identification; piecemeal benchmarks focused on specific research questions; simultaneous encoding of video and multilingual speech for instantaneous, realistic translation and dubbing. These challenges require a trans-national effort and are naturally suited to a European supercomputing initiative. Such models would increase exchange of knowledge across the EU, e.g. by enabling a seamless exchange of materials for training, teaching, or outreach, and supporting the traversal of multinational legal literature corpora.

Scalability and Efficiency

Large AI models, reaching trillions of parameters, present both opportunities and challenges. It is crucial to address issues related to training costs, inference efficiency, and the environmental impact. Larger text-only LLMs can reach low levels of perplexity scores with fewer training epochs but they require (at least) proportionally larger computational resources. Larger FMs need larger datasets, and grounding on non-text world representations, which for scientific applications can include widely heterogeneous data formats. The scaling between model size and required data is field-specific, e.g., in protein LMs the returns from larger models plateau fairly fast.

FMs also have high computational requirements during inference. Techniques like

quantization or pruning can reduce the model size (hence computing costs) at the expense of precision. Other solutions need to be investigated, including the co-design of specific inference hardware.

Architectural Innovations in FMs

While transformer models have recently dominated the FM landscape, there is a growing interest in alternative architectures such as State Space Models (including Mamba S4) and xLSTM. These models offer unique advantages and efficiencies that can complement existing AI technologies.

Ethics, Explainability, and Quality

We can identify a common set of criteria to assess ethics considerations on AI models.

- **Bias and Robustness.** Developing robust benchmarks to evaluate AI models, quantifying any possible bias and monitor their performance reliability across various scenarios, including robustness against catastrophic forgetting.
- **Quality Data.** Emphasising the need for high-quality training datasets to improve model accuracy and fairness, as well as monitoring semantic drift in LLMs.
- **Safety and Security.** Monitoring the reliability of AI models in safety critical applications (e.g. reward-hacking in RL, hallucinations in LLMs), safety against attacks that recover the training data (e.g. gradient inversion attacks). Different algorithms have been proposed to deliver safe RL training and deployment [7] or for the alignment of generative AI [8].
- **Explainability, interpretability, inspectability.** Some model classes allow human operators to garner a more transparent understanding of their internal working and decisions. Model-agnostic tools are available to inspect underlying assumptions on the data and which features are more strongly driving the model inference. In LLMs, these aspects can be surfaced via

careful prompting, e.g. in chain-of-thought or knowledge-graph grounding approaches.

- **Privacy and Intellectual Property.** Protecting personal details against extraction from a trained model, especially in federated-learning initiatives; extending opt-out rights and wide IP protection to individuals whose private data are used in LLM and visual model training; stress-testing anonymisation in AI models for healthcare.
- **Dual and malicious use.** Safeguarding AI models to adhere to EU policies on dual-use technology; anticipating and future-proofing risks of malicious use; training AI models to track suspicious activity related to malicious use of other AI models.
- **Compliance:** Ensuring AI models adhere to the latest AI regulations and standards, mitigating potential risks and legal implications. Guidelines have been published by the ISO and BSI (e.g. the BSI PAS440:2020, ISO/IEC 42001/2023). The AI Act (March 2024) set specific provisions for General-Purpose AI.

Accessibility

It is important to address the challenges of running AI applications (particularly LLMs) in environments that lack access to large-scale cloud infrastructure. Lowering the barrier to entry for deploying LLM services on-premises (such as in hospitals, classified systems, or air-gapped networks) is essential for broader societal benefit. This is especially critical for organizations that cannot rely on public cloud solutions due to privacy, security, or regulatory concerns.

Solutions like NVIDIA's NIMs, which allow users to download and run micro-services locally, provide a pathway for more organizations to utilize these technologies without cloud dependency. By emphasizing on-premises deployment options, AI technologies can be made more accessible, benefiting sectors where secure, localized AI processing is vital. This shift is necessary to ensure that AI advancements reach a broader audience beyond the cloud-centric paradigm of today.

Strategic Recommendations ETP4HPC

Applications Across Sectors

Foundation models are being applied in diverse sectors, including healthcare, education, regulatory compliance, scientific computing, and industry. Each sector presents unique challenges and opportunities that can be addressed through specialised AI applications.

Quantum AI

The intersection of AI and quantum computing is a burgeoning area of research. AI-driven optimization of quantum circuits and problem embedding showcases the potential for AI to enhance quantum computing capabilities. Please refer to the chapter on Quantum Computing for further recommendations.

Approach to Content Development

The content development approach for AI and foundation models should include a thorough review of current technologies and challenges like scalability, efficiency, and bias. It should involve collaboration with stakeholders from academia, industry, and government to ensure relevance. The focus should be on creating specialized content for areas such as fine-tuning techniques and multi-modal integration, while addressing ethical and regulatory concerns.

Comprehensive Review of Existing Literature, Research Papers and Technologies

Conduct a thorough review of current AI technologies, focusing on both transformer and non-transformer models, and their applications across different sectors.

Identification of Key Challenges and Opportunities

Identify the primary challenges, such as scalability, efficiency, and bias, and explore the opportunities presented by advancements in multi-modal AI and quantum computing.

Engagement with Stakeholders

Collaborate with stakeholders from academia, industry, and government to gather diverse perspectives and insights. This will ensure that the content is relevant and addresses the real-world needs of various sectors. Recent work re-examines the implications of traditional “stakeholder analysis” [9,10,11].

Development of Specialized Content

Create specialised content that addresses the unique requirements of different thematic areas. This includes detailed discussions on fine-tuning techniques, architectural innovations, and the integration of multi-modal data.

Ethical and Regulatory Considerations

As per the EU AI Act, models that require more than 10^{25} FLOPs are considered to pose *systemic risks* and are subject to more stringent scrutiny. Also for smaller models, common measures include: sandboxing of AI models, testing against adversarial examples and known attack strategies (including adversarial examples, prompt injection, gradient inversion) [12,13], identification of security and cybersecurity requirements [14], risk assessment and stakeholder analyses. The OECD actively maintains a catalogue of AI incidents and near-misses [15].

The “AREA” framework of Responsible Innovation [16] articulates four main phases. Anticipate: describe and analyse impact, intended

and unintended, and implications. Allow for further discovery rather than strive to predict all possible impact at the onset. Reflect: Purpose and motivations of the intended research/product/ activity, as well as uncertainties, assumptions, open questions and social transformations. Engage: Broader deliberation, inclusive consultation, iteration. Act: Use the above to influence and adjust the trajectory of the R&D activity.

Ongoing discussions on ethical considerations and regulatory compliance emphasise the importance of developing AI models that are trustworthy and reliable. Stakeholders of Responsible AI innovation can be individual users, groups, society and the environment. Impact on these stakeholders can be identified via five questions:

1. Who or what might benefit from the proposed innovation?
2. How likely and significant are the benefits?
3. What are the risks of other foreseeable use, misuse, dual use, malicious use?
4. Who might be at risk from misuse, dual use, or malicious use?
5. Can bias be created or reinforced, and how is it going to be assessed?

The assessment is recommended along five questions:

1. Is any of the above specific to a domain/ area?
2. What is the plan to mitigate risks arising from this product/ research/ activity?
3. How likely are the identified risks?
4. How severe would the impact be?
5. How is this going to be communicated with project partners and stakeholders?

A guide for assessment of technical and non-technical aspects of AI Trustworthiness has been assembled by the European Commission's the High-Level Expert Group on AI [17].

Future Trends and Vision

Here we provide an outlook on future trends in AI, by highlighting potential advancements and their implications for foundational models. This includes exploring the post-exascale vision and the role of AI in driving further technological and scientific breakthroughs.

By following this approach, we aim to provide a comprehensive and forward-looking perspective on AI foundation models, guiding future research and development efforts to maximise their impact across various sectors.

Use Cases

Earth Sciences: The introduction of Foundation Models to Earth Sciences has significant potential to advance multiple domains with the four key areas being:

- a. **Biodiversity:** Large-scale models trained on vast multi-modal datasets including (images, audio, eDNA, species maps) can be used for species identification and classification, habitat mapping and monitoring while also predicting biodiversity patterns like population dynamics and biodiversity hotspots, aiding in conservation planning [18].
- b. **Weather:** In the field of meteorology, FMs can enhance weather forecasting and analysis by learning from vast historical weather data and current observations, predict extreme events when fine-tuned to detect patterns associated with hurricanes, tornadoes, and heatwaves with potential of improving early warning systems. Because of their power to integrate data from multiple sources (satellites, ground stations, radar) and fill in gaps where observations are missing, they can provide a more complete picture of atmospheric conditions [19].
- c. **Climate:** FMs offer new approaches to understanding and predicting long-term trends by integrating as the backbones of climate model emulators, perform complex climate pattern recognition and teleconnections while also help to bridge the gap

between global climate models and local impacts.

- d. **Earth:** FMs excel at geospatial analysis when trained on earth observations and other geospatial data with downstream tasks in land use classification, urban planning and monitoring deforestation or agricultural practices. Because of their ability to rapidly analyse post-disaster data like imagery, damage assessment and guidance for response efforts for events like earthquakes, floods or wildfires is of paramount importance. In the same theme, one of the pillars of human prosperity, agriculture can gain a lot of benefits like smart crop management, disease detect and yield monitoring [20]. ECMWF and DestinE research are a particularly strong influencer here [21].

Smart Cities & Urban Planning: FMs can advance smart cities and urban planning. Using multiple data sources (EO, sensor networks, social media, etc) patterns can be identified and future trends in urban development, population growth and land use changes can be predicted. Various urban services can be enhanced by processing and integrating diverse data streams, e.g. optimise traffic flow by analysing real-time traffic data, weather conditions, and even schedules, or improve waste management by predicting waste generation patterns and optimising collection routes [22].

Aerospace: Similar to the other domains, FMs can significantly enhance various aspects of the aerospace industry, from design optimization and predictive maintenance to flight operations and space exploration [23].

Smart Industry: FMs can be the springboard for manufacturing and industrial automation mainly because they can analyse vast amounts of different sensor data to predict equipment failures before they occur, reducing downtime and maintenance costs. These models can be used for automated visual inspection, detecting defects in products with high accuracy, boosting the quality control. A lot of industrial processes can be further optimised where FMs can suggest improvements in manufacturing processes. Additionally, a new way of user interfacing is introduced with these models, currently by chat and voice but in the future in 3d space and via BMI that can further increase productivity.

Material Science: Our reality is material-based, thus multidisciplinary integration is required to solve the problems of the future and FMs can integrate multiple representations of materials on a united latent space, enabling overarching modelling across different disciplines. Due to their property of vast amounts of data analysis for prediction, they excel in predicting material properties, potentially accelerating the discovery of new materials - similar to proteins [24].

Healthcare: FMs show significant potential in offering personalised treatment plans by processing many patient data. They can serve as diagnostic assistance processing medical images, patient records and genetic data to aid in disease identification and diagnosis. In the same way they operate in material science, they can accelerate the drug discovery process by predicting potential drug candidates and their interactions [25]. EHRs contain invaluable information about patients and have shown to have strong predictive capability in a wealth of applications ranging from patient care to administrative concerns like bed occupancy, probability of readmission, insurance issues, etc. Research in EHRs is hindered by privacy concerns and presents issues generalising across hospitals, even in the same health systems. Improving research in these areas will require solutions to the problems of data access, such as federated environments, trusted computational environments, or the ability to generate appropriate synthetic datasets that can sidestep these issues.

Bioinformatics and Molecular Biology: Biological sequences are a natural application domain for LLMs. FMs trained over vast datasets of protein sequences available from all sorts of organisms, from humans to bacteria, helps us understand their diversity, predict their 3D structure and relate that to their function and how they interact in biological systems. DNA foundational models can be used to understand the nature of different genomic sequences, their function (e.g. how they affect gene expression), or their evolution (e.g. how viral strains evolve during a pandemic). Some of the main challenges for protein LMs is to create datasets to fine-tune on particular tasks of interest in research or industry, such as predicting thermostability. In the case of genomic sequences there are architectural challenges related to the extremely large size of genomic sequences, which show a costly quadratic scaling in conventional transformer architectures. Biological sequences have important implications for data privacy and for societal safety. FM models may need to be probed for their ability to accelerate development of biological threats by malicious parties.

Regional Security and Resilience: One of the main challenges is interoperability, e.g. for defence (including NATO), national security, and transport or energy infrastructure. Allies operate different systems, collect variable data and at the end of the day, they need to collaborate. FMs can solve this problem by integrating vast data streams and providing a generic framework on which down-stream multimodal tasks can be solved. Further applications as decision support systems can aid the explainable decision making in higher command under volatile and uncertain situations [26].

Beyond Exascale

The transition to post-exascale supercomputing marks a significant milestone in the evolution of AI and foundation models, offering unparalleled computational power and efficiency. This paper explores the potential innovations and impacts of post-exascale supercomputing on AI, emphasizing scalability, efficiency, and sustainability. We will also discuss the distinctive computing power requirements for AI training and inference, and the consequent evolution of micro-architectures and data utilization strategies.

Scalability & Efficiency

As we move into the post-exascale era, the ability to train AI models with billions or even trillions of parameters will become increasingly feasible. Training these vast models necessitates the use of capability clusters, specifically designed to handle the immense computational loads. Unlike traditional numerical simulations, AI training does not require high floating-point precision, leading to a shift from 64-bit to 32-bit arithmetic circuits in advanced micro-architectures. This adaptation optimizes the silicon area and enhances the efficiency of AI training processes.

To fully leverage the capabilities of post-exascale supercomputers, it is crucial to integrate advanced scalable mathematical methods and algorithms employing also advanced parallelism techniques, including data, model, operation, pipeline, and sequence parallelism. Memory-efficient strategies like checkpointing, offloading, and mixed-precision arithmetic will further enhance the scalability and efficiency of

AI training on next-generation heterogeneous systems (with GPU accelerators).

Technologies like SDN, innovative networks (photonics), virtualisation, programmable switches, and memory interconnects contribute to more efficient scaling and management of HPC environments, making them better suited to handle increasingly complex AI workloads.

High-performance storage and IO infrastructure

These are critical components of AI workflows and must be emphasized to fully support the data-intensive nature of modern AI workloads. One key recommendation is to architect, develop, and operate HPC infrastructure as robust data ingestion and processing engines. This involves not only providing large-scale storage capacity but also tightly integrating data and compute services to ensure seamless performance across the workflow. AI workloads often require massive data movement and processing, which necessitates high-throughput, low-latency storage solutions. By optimizing IO and storage infrastructure, HPC environments can become more efficient at managing data-intensive tasks, enhancing overall performance and scalability. Computational Storage is becoming more relevant nowadays and can help to reduce data movement and latency.

Data Utilization and Synthetic Data

The availability and quality of training data remain pivotal for developing high-performing AI models. In the coming years, traditional data sources will be thoroughly exploited, necessitating the generation of new and synthetic datasets. Post-exascale supercomputers will play a critical role in creating these synthetic datasets through precise simulations, providing fresh and high-quality data essential for continuous AI model improvement. This approach will ensure the sustained growth and advancement

of AI technologies despite the eventual exhaustion of existing data sources.

Inference: Capacity Over Capability

Inference in AI, particularly for large models, is more about capacity than capability. The transition from numerical kernels to neuronal approaches will require handling millions of parallel model calls efficiently. Each call, being independent, necessitates a system designed for high-throughput, low-latency processing. This requirement will likely lead to the development of specialized partitions, akin to the GPU clusters of the 2000s, optimized for the unique demands of AI inference.

Environmental Impact and Sustainability

The environmental impact of AI training and inference is a growing concern. Post-exascale supercomputing must prioritize energy-efficient hardware and software solutions to mitigate these effects. Techniques like model quantization can significantly reduce the computational and energy requirements of AI models. Additionally, incorporating renewable energy sources and sustainable practices in supercomputing centres will be crucial to reducing the carbon footprint of AI development.

Ethical Considerations and Explainability

With the increased power and complexity of AI models, ensuring ethical use and explainability is more important than ever. Post-exascale systems must include robust mechanisms for monitoring and mitigating biases, and tools for explaining AI decision-making processes. These measures will help build trust in AI technologies, ensuring they are used responsibly and ethically.

Post-Exascale Recommendations

The post-exascale era offers immense potential for advancing AI and foundation models, provided we address the challenges of scalability, efficiency, sustainability, and ethics. The following recommendations are crucial to realizing this potential:

- **Invest in Energy-Efficient Technologies:** Develop and adopt energy-efficient hardware and software solutions to minimize the environmental impact of AI training and deployment.
- **Enhance Parallelism Techniques:** Implement advanced parallelism strategies to optimize computational efficiency, scalability and networking for large AI models.
- **Foster Ethical AI Development:** Ensure that AI models adhere to ethical guidelines and are explainable and transparent to stakeholders.
- **Promote Interdisciplinary Collaboration:** Encourage collaboration between AI researchers, supercomputing experts, and domain scientists to leverage AI in various fields effectively.
- **Support Sustainable Infrastructure:** Utilize renewable energy sources and sustainable practices in supercomputing centres to reduce the carbon footprint of AI development.

By addressing these recommendations, we can harness the full potential of post-exascale supercomputing to drive innovation and societal progress through advanced AI technologies.

Overall Conclusions

Supercomputing plays a crucial role in advancing AI and foundation models, enabling the handling of complex tasks and large datasets. Addressing the challenges related to data quality, ethical alignment, model evaluation, and environmental impact is essential for sustainable and reliable AI development. Ongoing research into alternative architectures, multi-modal capabilities, and specialized models will continue to drive innovation in this field, ensuring that AI technologies meet diverse needs and applications effectively.

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